

EMPLOYEE SATISFACTION TOWARDS VICKY'S HI-STYLE FURNITURE, DINDIGUL DISTRICT, TAMIL NADU, INDIA: AN ANALYTICAL STUDY

S. Preethi Sowmia*, V. Tamilselvi & Dr. B. Velmurugan*****

* PG Scholar, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

** Associate Professor, Department of MBA, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

*** Associate professor & HOD, Department of Management Studies, NPR College of Engineering & Technology, Dindigul, Tamilnadu

Cite This Article: S. Preethi Sowmia, V. Tamilselvi & Dr. B. Velmurugan, "Employee Satisfaction towards Vicky's Hi-Style Furniture, Dindigul District, Tamil Nadu, India: An Analytical Study", International Journal of Applied and Advanced Scientific Research, Volume 8, Issue 1, Page Number 64-67, 2023.

Abstract:

The Project has been done in Vicky's Hi-style Furniture. The title of the project is "A Study on Employee Satisfaction". The main objective of the study is to find out the overall satisfaction level of employees in the company. In the company I have studied thoroughly the working method and functions of the Human Resource department individually. The collected data was analyzed by using relevant tools such as Percentage analysis, Chi Square test, and Correlation analysis. It reflects the thoughts of the researcher in the form of findings, suggestions and conclusions. In the appendix various supporting information have been incorporated for an easy understanding of the readers.

About Vicky's Hi-Style Furniture:

Vick's the brand from the House of Hi - Style products. Hi Style Products in Sithayankottai, Dindigul is known to satisfactorily cater to the demands of its customer base. It stands located at 9-1-1E/1, Sedapatti, Dindigul Road, Ganapathi Street, Sithayankottai - 624708. Sedapatti is a prominent landmark in the area and this establishment is in close proximity to the same. The business strives to make for a positive experience through its offerings. The prominent name in south India, manufacturing furniture for more than 25 years stands for quality, Strength and durable for your wallets. Is well equipped with German, Turkey and Taiwan machinery, which enable high technology production manufacturing capability.

The production facilities are placed in well equipped production shops having a total covered area of more than 53,800 s.q.ft. The production capacity is around 1400 sq.m/ day. Brand Vicky's is launched in 2014 from the house of HI-STYLE Products,, the company that has its manufacturing base in central part of Tamilnadu. The total space used for manufacturing purpose is 100,000 square meter and the storage space amounts to 25,000 square meters. Strict adherence to quality has enabled us me said on the top in the industry since our inception. We use only E2, E1, E0, Grade particle boards that gives more life span to the furniture, stringent checking process takes place on various stages to deliver products of superior quality.

As business grow larger, so does the organization therefore, the entire business is divided into functions under each process. At the outset, all the processes which are strictly documented are operating processes which transform inputs to outputs. As business grow larger, so does the organization therefore, the entire business is divided into functions under each process. At the outset, all the processes which are strictly documented are operating processes which transform inputs to outputs. Customer centricity is at the core of Hi Style Products in Sithayankottai, Dindigul and it is this belief that has led the business to build long-term relationships. Ensuring a positive customer experience, making available goods and/or services that are of top-notch quality is given prime importance. India's leading B2B market place, Jd Mart ensures engaging in business activities is a seamless process for small and medium enterprises as well as large businesses. In a wake to enable these businesses to reach their audience, this portal lets them showcase their offerings in terms of the products and/or services through a digital catalogue. This business has a wide range of product offerings and the product/catalogue list includes Bed, Dining Table, Antique Dressing Table, Dressing Table, Furniture etc.

Employee Satisfaction:

- At the root of a lot of stress, anxiety, and frustration that many employees feel are unrealistic expectations from the organization.
- Recognizing your employees is one of the easiest and cheapest ways to increase job satisfaction.
- The lack of communication is the source of a lot of frustration in the workplace. Knowledge is power, so there's no reason why you shouldn't want to empower your employees with as much as available.
- Employees want feedback vigorously and aren't as sensitive as you might think. There is no need to be rude with your feedback, but if you are straightforward and honest, employees will respect that.

Review of Literature:

Allen and Meyer, 1996; Karrasch, 2003 - Organization commitment can be defined as affiliation of employees to the organization and involvement in it. In general there are three dimensions of commitment

which are continuance commitment, affective commitment and normative commitment.

Judge, Timothy A.; Thoresen, Carl J.; Bono, Joyce E.; Patton, Gregory K. *Psychological Bulletin*, Vol 127(3), May 2001 - A qualitative and quantitative review of the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance is provided. The qualitative review is organized around 7 models that characterize past research on the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance.

Srivastava (2004) - The Impact of Labour Welfare on Employees Attitudes and Job Satisfaction, a comparative study was conducted on workers in the private and public sectors of Kanpur city. The researcher attempted to assess the quality of labour welfare activities; measure the degree of job satisfaction of workers provided with labour welfare facilities in private and public sectors and evaluates the attitudes of workers towards management in both the sectors.

Warn (2003) emphasized aspects of the workplace, contributing to depression and lack of job satisfaction. Stress is normally caused by a lack of power over the intended effects. At the workplace, tension is felt because of a lack of authority, job conflicts, and uncertainty, contributing to frustration. The principle of checkability brings a solution to lower pressures and contributes to job fulfillment in which a person has an attitude of desires and needs that depends on the aspirations of the individual and governs multiple facets of the working situation. A supportive working atmosphere, such as a positive environment for studying or no abuse at work or anxiety in the workplace, helps minimize depression and achieve job satisfaction.

Zaki (2003) Explains Lebanese non-management banking employees' work satisfaction and results. The researchers found a substantial link in terms of pay and supervision between work satisfaction and gender. Only satisfied people within the company are willing to carry out their roles and obligations. Women workers were happy with the salaries, while men were happier with supervision. The author himself often claims this does not matter because the self-rate is inflated, and his colleagues' success is usually underestimated.

Mullins, (2005), Employee satisfaction is a complex and multifaceted concept which can mean different things to different people. Job satisfaction is usually linked with motivation, but the nature of this relationship is not clear. Satisfaction is not the same as motivation. Job satisfaction is more of an attitude, an internal state. It could, for example, be associated with a personal feeling of achievement, quantitative.

Austin (2007) the major reasons for managers' work satisfaction in Cyprus are "selffulfillment," "independence," and "job environment." Fair salaries, well-educated subordinates, the prospects for self-realization are development opportunities. Employers can reflect on the three aspects of community independence of their work setting to ensure the framework's flow contributes to job satisfaction, i.e., age, sex, number of years in the company, public and private sector, number of workers oversaw.

Ramayah (2011) evaluates whether mentoring results in work satisfaction within the Malaysian context. His results suggest that career mentoring is connected to every aspect of work satisfaction. The aspects of job satisfaction analyzed were: jobs themselves, employees, managers, and promotion. At a higher education level, mentors often play an important role and deliver meaningful job results directly. But psychological mentoring has no essential connection to the three variables that fulfill the job (co-workers, the job itself, and promotion).

Singh & Jain (2016), Employee happiness and its impact on results were highlighted. The behavior of workers represents the company's morality. The satisfied staff has a significant role in customer care and sales because they communicate regularly with the customer. The office is the gateway to employee fulfillment. Good labor practices and good working conditions also improve workers' efficiency, profitability, satisfaction, and retention.

Objective of the Study:

- To identify the various activities are conducted in the organization.
- To identify and analyze the employees working condition.
- To identify the basic facilities are given to the employees.
- To identify the employee satisfaction inside the organization

Scope of the Study:

- The main scope of this study about the satisfaction level of employees in the organization.
- Promoting and maintaining overall wellbeing of workers in all occupations.
- This study helps to analyse and practice the human resource work.
- This study helps to identify overall performance of HI-STYLE Products.
- It further explains the area on which employees are mostly dissatisfied.
- Job satisfaction of the employees has been analyzed on the basis of the following seventeen job related factors.

Research Design:

This study involves the descriptive research design. It includes surveys and fact findings of different kinds, which is one of the most suitable ways to carry out projects. The main purpose of this research design is it has no control over the variables. The study was conducted for a period of 3 months. The type of research conducted was descriptive, because the employee's opinions are qualitative in nature. It can only be analyzed

and described.

Descriptive Research Design:

In this research study, the researcher has used descriptive research design. Descriptive study, Who, What, When, Where, How are the questions for researcher to find their answers during the study. A descriptive study may be simple or complex. This research study topic is according to the descriptive study.

Sampling:

The basic idea of sampling is that by selecting some of the sample from the population, researcher may draw conclusions about the sample study and generalize for entire population.

Sample Size:

Sample size is a part of target population, carefully selected to represent the population. The overall population are 350 and sample size are 110 employees.

Research Methodology:

Research Methodology is a way the systematically solve the research problem. Research methodology may be understood as a science of studying how research is done scientifically. In this study the descriptive research design was adopted, since it includes surveys and fact- findings enquire of different kinds, which is one of the most suitable ways t carry out projects.

Method of Data Collection:

Sources of Data:

Primary Data:

Primary data are collected afresh and for the first time, it us the data originated by the researcher specifically t address the research problem. In this study, primary data is collected through questionnaire. To understand the employee satisfaction in the organization.

Secondary Data:

Secondary data is collected from internet, registers, records, journals, articles, magazines and annual reports f the organization.

Tools for Data Analysis and Interpretation:

In order to do the work properly, an insight about the product, about the organization, about the employees was necessary. For this purpose an extensive study was initially done about the Employee Satisfaction after the initial study, the survey was started in order to get the questionnaire filled by them.

Analytical Tools for the Study:

- Percentage Analysis
- Chi - square test
- Correlation Analysis

Correlation or dependence is any statistical relationship, whether casual or not, between two random variables.

Limitations of the Study:

- The study was restricted to the limited employees.
- The response from the people may be biased.
- The sample size limited to respondents.
- The study has the time restrictions.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Management Sympathetic towards Problem Solving in Work Station

Problem Solving	No of Respondents	Percentage
To Some Extent	23	20.90%
To Large Extent	87	79.09%
Total	110	100%

Interpretation:

In the above table shows that out of 110 respondents, that the majority of respondents opinion were 79.09% to large extent, 79.09% are to some extent.

Table 2: Employees Satisfaction Level towards Reasonable Salary for the Work Done

Salary	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	86	78.18%
No	24	21.81%
Total	110	100%

Interpretation:

In the above table shows that out of 110 respondents, that the 78.18% majority of respondents were agreed getting salary based on the work they done and 21.81% didn't agree.

Table 3: Employees Opinion About Observed any Discrimination in the Company

Discrimination	No of Respondents	Percentage
Racial Discrimination	-	-

Sexual Harassment	-	-
Gender Discrimination	5	4.54%
Sexual Orientation Discrimination	-	-
None Observed	105	95.45%
Total	110	100%

Interpretation:

In the above table shows that out of 110 respondents, that the 95.45% majority of respondents doesn't observed the problem of discrimination, 4.54% has faced gender discrimination and no one faced racial discrimination, sexual orientation problem.

Findings:

- Majority of the employees respond that the management will be sympathetic towards the employees.
- Most of the employees have been satisfied with the facilities provided in the company.
- The employees in the organization having the cordial relationship with the workers.
- 81.8% of the respondent accepted that the company policy is really based on the employee protection.
- The majority of the respondent has no problem with the present setup of the management.
- The respondent doesn't faced any kind of discrimination than 4.54% of gender discrimination.

Suggestion:

- The company may recruit more experienced persons for better productivity.
- The salary provided for the employees can be increased.
- More said manual handling is the major cause of accident, so the company may partly turns their process as mechanized or automated.
- The warehouses were full of dust, so the term cleanliness cold be followed.
- Every employee is bound to be having certain safety measure, so the company may need to improve more safety measures.
- Company can have given a chance for arranging a vocation for their employee's mental health.

Conclusion:

As a part of our project work, I got an opportunity to spend a period of three months in Vicky's Hi-Style Furniture. It helped me to analyze the working of the organization which helped as to convert our theoretical knowledge into practical. The present study is an earnest attempt to determine employee's satisfaction in Vicky's Hi-Style Furniture. It is indeed necessary for any organization to understand the need of their employees and fulfill them before they leave the organization. If nothing is done by the organization then there are chances to lose talented employees from any organization to its competitors. Hence it is necessary for any organization to ensure employees satisfaction. From the study it was identified that the most of the employees are satisfied with the job. Majority of the employees are satisfied with the salary structure, promotional programs, working condition, allowances provided by the organization. They are also satisfied with the employer-employee relationship and communication channel in the organization. Employees get opportunities. If the firm concentrates of the findings and suggestions of their survey, we hopefully believe that the organization can further bring out their labor with full satisfaction and obtain good result.

References:

1. Alex Edmans, (2011), Does the stock market fully value intangibles? Employee satisfaction and equity prices, *Journal of Financial Economics*: (pp. 621-640).
2. Afshan Naseem, Sadia Ejaz Sheikh & Khusro P. Malik, (2011), Impact of Employee Satisfaction on Success of Organization: Relation between Customer Experience and Employee Satisfaction, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Sciences and Engineering*: Vol.2 No.5.
3. Ahmad Jamal Tahir, Rosman Bin Md. Yusoff, Anwar Khan, Kamran Azam , Muhammad Sohaib Ahmed & Muhammad Zohair Sahoo, (2011), A Comparison of Intrinsic and Extrinsic Compensation Instruments: The Case of National Bank of Pakistan (NBP), District Attock, Pakistan, *World Journal of Social Sciences*: Vol. 1 No.4 (pp.195-206).
4. Ana-Maria Godeanu, (2012), The antecedents of satisfaction with pay in teams: do performance-based compensation and autonomy keep team-members satisfied, *Eastern Journal of European Studies*: Vol. 3 No. 1 (pp. 145 - 168).
5. Abdul Sattar1, Allah Nawaz and Shadiullah Khan, (2012), The contextual impacts on job satisfaction of employees in the developing states like Pakistan, *Universal Journal of Education and General Studies*: Vol. 1 No. 5 (pp. 136-145).
6. Anastasios Palaiologos, Panagiotis Papazekos & Leda Panayotopoulou, (2011), "Organizational justice and employee satisfaction in performance appraisal", *Journal of European Industrial Training*: Vol. 35 No. 8 (pp.826 - 840).